

Polarography of Bromate Ions in Aqueous Organic Solvent Mixtures

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THE polarographic behaviour of bromate ion was first reported by Rylich¹. He found a single wave corresponding to direct reduction to bromide ion. He also observed that the decomposition potential of the bromate became more positive with increase in the valency of cation and with increasing concentration of the supporting electrolyte. These results were confirmed by Kolthoff and Lingane^{2,3}. The effect of pH on the reduction of bromate was carried out by Orlemann and Kolthoff⁴. Zykov *et al.*⁵ studied the reduction of bromate ion at d.m.e. in neutral, acidic and alkaline medium. It appears that no attention has been paid so far towards the reduction of bromate ion in aqueous organic solvent mixtures. The present paper deals with the polarographic behaviour of bromate ion in different aqueous mixtures of formamide, N-methyl formamide, dimethyl formamide, acetonitrile and dioxan.

Experimental

Stock solutions of BrO_3^- (0.01M) and NaOH (1.0M) were prepared by dissolving required weight of reagent grade KBrO_3 and NaOH in doubly distilled water and both were standardised as usual⁶. Solvent supplied by commercial sources were purified and distilled by standard methods⁷.

Solutions containing 1mM BrO_3^- and 0.1M NaOH having different percentage of solvents (by volume) were prepared in 25 ml volumetric flasks. Solutions were also prepared having different BrO_3^- ions concentrations in same percentage of organic solvents with 0.1M NaOH. The current-voltage curves were obtained by a Radiometer PO_4 . The dropping mercury electrode having $m = 1.1464$ mg/sec. and $t = 5.0$ secs. (with applied potential of -1.0 V vs S.C.E. at 50 cm of mercury pressure in 0.1M NaOH), was used for all the measurements. All the experiments were performed at 30° , which was maintained by a Hakke type ultra thermostat. The H type cell with a agar-agar plug saturated with KCl was used for all the measurements. The solutions were freed from dissolved oxygen by bubbling purified N_2 gas for 30 mins, which was pre-saturated with solution of same solvent composition. The I.R. drop correction was applied wherever needed. For this purpose L.P. conduscope was utilised. The viscosity of the solutions were measured by an Ostwald viscometer.

Results and Discussion

The current-voltage curves were obtained in 10, 20, 40 and 60 percent (by volume) of the formamide,

N-methyl formamide, N-N' dimethyl formamide, acetonitrile and dioxan. In case of acetonitrile and dioxan the measurements could not be extended above 40 percent due to the formation of layer. In each case well-defined single reduction wave appeared. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} (h = effective height of mercury column) were linear and passed through origin for all the aqueous organic solvent mixtures, showing that the electrode reactions were diffusion controlled. The same results were confirmed from the plots of i_d vs C (bromate ion concentration) which were linear and passed through origin. The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ ($-V$ vs S.C.E.) were linear for all the solvent mixtures. The values of these slopes were found to be much higher than that required for 6 electron reversible reduction (10 mV at 30°) suggesting that the reductions were highly irreversible

The value of D (diffusion coefficient) for BrO_3^- in all the organic aqueous mixtures have been calculated by using Ilkovic equation and it was found that diffusion coefficient decreased with increasing proportions of the organic solvents. But in case of formamide it increased slightly.

The half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) values were obtained by the intercept of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. It has been observed that $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative value with increasing percentage of the solvent by volume. But the reverse results were obtained in case of with increasing percentage of the solvent by volume. But the reverse results were obtained in case of acetonitrile and dioxan.

The diffusion current (i_d) was found to increase in case of formamide, acetonitrile and dioxane and in case of N-methyl formamide and dimethyl formamide i_d decreases with increasing percentage of the organic solvent. As the reductions were irreversible the kinetic parameters K°_{fh} (rate constant at zero volt) and αn (transfer coefficient) were calculated by Koutecky's method⁸. The plots of $\log K^{\circ}_{fh}$ vs E ($-V$ vs N.H.E.) were linear for all the aqueous organic solvent mixtures. The extrapolation of the line to zero volt vs N.H.E. gave the value of K°_{fh} , whereas αn was obtained from the slope of the plot. The standard rate constant can not be obtained for such systems, because the value of standard electrode potential is not known in all the aqueous organic solvent mixtures. However the approximate value of $K^{\circ}_{s'}$, can be obtained by extrapolation from the plots of $-\log K^{\circ}_{fh}$ vs E ($-V$ vs N.H.E.) at 0.61 V, which is the standard electrode potential for BrO_3^- in alkaline medium⁹. The kinetic parameters and polarographic characteristics are summarised in Table 1.

The value of ' αn ' increases or decreases slightly with weight percentage of organic solvents; but the value of αn is slightly higher in aqueous organic solvent mixtures than in aqueous medium, which shows that number of electrons involved in the rate determining step is almost same in all the aqueous organic solvent mixtures.

TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR REDUCTION OF BROMATE ION (1mM) IN DIFFERENT AQUEOUS ORGANIC SOLVENT MIXTURES

Solvent	Percentage (by vol.)	i_d (uA)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	Slope (mV)	$D^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec)	K_{fh}^0 (cm/sec)	K_s^0 (cm/sec)	αn
Water	—	16.5	1.882	120	3.3740	1.12×10^{-16}	1.12×10^{-16}	0.48
Formamide	10	14.0	1.731	78	2.8599	5.25×10^{-15}	7.94×10^{-10}	0.47
	20	14.5	1.741	74	2.9620	5.01×10^{-16}	3.16×10^{-11}	0.52
	40	15.0	1.747	90	3.0641	3.98×10^{-17}	1.00×10^{-12}	0.56
	60	15.5	1.752	91	3.1663	1.26×10^{-18}	1.99×10^{-13}	0.57
N-methyl formamide	10	15.0	1.671	93	3.0641	8.91×10^{-15}	6.31×10^{-10}	0.50
	20	13.5	1.702	67	2.7577	7.94×10^{-17}	1.12×10^{-12}	0.58
	40	11.5	1.721	69	2.3492	7.08×10^{-18}	7.94×10^{-13}	0.59
	60	14.5	1.742	74	2.9620	8.91×10^{-19}	6.31×10^{-13}	0.60
N-N' dimethyl formamide	10	13.5	1.649	73	2.7577	1.26×10^{-16}	6.31×10^{-10}	0.52
	20	12.0	1.655	65	2.4513	7.94×10^{-17}	6.31×10^{-11}	0.60
	40	11.5	1.706	70	2.3492	6.31×10^{-20}	5.62×10^{-13}	0.69
	60	14.5	1.739	82	2.9620	8.91×10^{-21}	7.94×10^{-14}	0.69
Acetonitrile	10	13.0	1.752	86	2.7577	4.21×10^{-17}	1.11×10^{-12}	0.54
	20	14.0	1.732	91	2.8599	1.78×10^{-17}	3.98×10^{-11}	0.54
	40	14.0	1.690	67.5	2.8599	1.11×10^{-17}	2.51×10^{-11}	0.55
Dioxane	10	11.0	1.714	92	2.2470	1.25×10^{-19}	3.98×10^{-12}	0.61
	20	12.0	1.686	96	2.4513	7.08×10^{-18}	3.55×10^{-12}	0.61
	40	14.5	1.640	82	2.9620	1.26×10^{-18}	6.31×10^{-11}	0.62

The electrode reaction of BrO_3^- in alkaline or neutral media has been explained by Klothoff and Lingane^{2,3}

and the electrode reaction of BrO_3^- in acid media has been explained by Kolthoff and Orlemann⁴

involving several steps)

according to them 6 electrons are involved. It is obvious from present results that polarographic characteristics ($E_{1/2}$, i_d and slope) for reduction of BrO_3^- change a little with the addition of formamide, acetonitrile, N-methyl formamide, dimethyl formamide and dioxan in aqueous alkaline solution suggesting that the electrode reaction essentially remain the same.

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